

Synthetic Aspects of Transition Metal Complexes of Tripodal Amines

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This compilation of information which has been collected on the synthetic and structural aspects of transition metal complexes of tripodal amines will be useful to the inorganic chemist. A most important aspect of the tripodal amine complexes which might command attention in the future is the extension of synthetic and structural studies of complexes with large ring sizes around the central metal atom. This would then afford some new information regarding the kinetic and thermodynamic behavior of these systems.

A. Introduction

TRIPODAL amines have been used as ligands in transition metal complexes since 1925, when Mann^{1a} prepared tren-complexes of some platinum metals. These were the first described in which an aliphatic tertiary nitrogen atom occupied a coordination position. Tren has since been found to form both five- and six-coordinate complexes with transition metal ions. Mann^{1b} also synthesized the propyl analog of tren (trpn), and prepared complexes of both tren and trpn with nickel(II) and some platinum metals.

We shall be concerned in this review with the preparation of the amine ligands and their complexes, as well as their structure and spectra. The thermochemistry, and kinetic behavior of some of these complexes were the subject of an earlier review article.²

B. Preparation

1. Ligands

a. *Tris (2-aminoethyl) amine (tren)*

The first preparation of tren was carried out in 1896 by Ristenpart³, who passed dry ammonia gas through molten β -bromethylphthalimide and extracted the crude product with ethanol to obtain triphthalimidotriethylamine (1)

The triphthalimidotriethylamine was hydrolyzed by heating small portions with concentrated hydrochloric

acid in a sealed tube. (2) The filtrate was then concentrated and poured into ethanol, which precipitated tren trihydrochloride. (3)

Mann^{1a} followed the same basic synthesis but hydrolyzed the triphthalimidotriethylamine in solution with dilute hydrochloric acid. Another method of hydrolyzing triphthalimidotriethylamine is to reflux it with ethanolic hydrazine⁴.

The triphthalimidotriethylamine can also be prepared⁵ by reacting triethanolamine with thionyl chloride. (4)

Tren trihydrochloride can be isolated from mixtures of tren and trien of varying composition. Technical grade tren contains about 5% tren, and several workers^{6,7} have isolated tren trihydrochloride by dissolving the mixture in ethanol and fractionally precipitating with dilute or concentrated hydrochloric acid at 5°.

Tren-tren mixtures containing 70-90% tren are available from Carbide and Carbon Chem. Corp. and from Dow Chem. Co. The pure amine can now also be purchased commercially.

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The trihydrochloride can be prepared from the free amine by reaction with sodium hydroxide and vacuum distillation^{6,7}, although yields appear to be very low in this procedure.

b. *Tris (3-aminopropyl) amine (trpn)*

Trpn appears to be more difficult to prepare than tren. Mann and Pope^{1b} prepared it in a manner similar to that used in the synthesis of tren

Yields are not given for any of the above syntheses and it is not known whether other workers have ever successfully repeated this procedure.

Interrante⁴ has prepared free trpn by reducing tricyanotriethylamine in a high pressure hydrogenation apparatus, in producing a 54% yield.

c. *4, 4', 4'' (triaminotributyl) amine (trbn)*

Trbn. 4HCl. H₂O, the butyl analogue of tren, has been prepared⁹. Potassium phthalimide and tetramethylene dibromide were reacted to give N(4-bromobutyl) phthalimide, into which anhydrous ammonia was passed to give 4, 4', 4'' triphthalimidotributylamine. This, when heated with concentrated hydrochloric acid and separated from the precipitated phthalic acid, gave trbn. 3HCl. H₂O

The coordinating properties of this ligand have not been investigated.

d. *Hexamethyl and hexaethyl derivatives*

Alkyl derivatives of tripodal amine ligands of the type N(CH₂)_nNR₂, where R=Me, Et and n=2, 3, 4 have been prepared⁹. The methyl derivatives can be produced by reductive methylation of the amine hydrochloride with formaldehyde and formic acid.

Methyl derivatives of tren, trpn, and trbn have been made by this method.

The hexaethyl derivative of tren has been prepared by the reaction of N, N-diethylethylenediamine and 2-chlorotriethylamine. The oil obtained was made alkaline, vacuum distilled and treated with ethanolic HCl. Presumably, ethyl derivatives of the other ligands could be made in this manner.

e. *1,1,1 Tris (dimethylaminomethyl) ethane (TSN) and 1,1,1 Tris (dimethylaminoethyl) ethane (TTN)*

TTN was prepared⁹ by the reaction of dimethylamine with 1,1,1-tris (bromomethyl) ethane in an autoclave at 160°. The crude product was distilled twice under reduced pressure. Pure TTN distilled at 33-34° (0.10mm) or 49° (5mm) and was obtained in 80% yield.

TSN was prepared similarly by the reaction of 1,1,1 tris (dimethylaminomethyl) ethane with anhydrous monoethylamine. It distilled at 38-39° (8mm), and 80% yield was obtained.

Table 1 gives some physical properties of the tripodal amines.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF TRIPODAL AMINES

Name	Formula	Phys. Form	M.P.	B.P.	Ref.
tren	$N(CH_2CH_2NH_2)_3$	clear to pale yellow liquid	°C	265-300	a
tren.3HCl	$N(CH_2CH_2NH_2)_3 \cdot 3HCl$	white solid	> 300		1
tren.4HCl	$N(CH_2CH_2NH_2)_3 \cdot 4HCl$	white solid	167-169		33b
Me ₆ tren.3HCl.H ₂ O	$N(CH_2CH_2NMe_2)_3 \cdot 3HCl \cdot H_2O$	white solid	276		9
Et ₆ tren.3HCl	$N(CH_2CH_2NEt_2)_3 \cdot 3HCl$	white solid	250-251		9
trpn	$N(CH_2CH_2CH_2CH_2NH_2)_3$	liquid		110-115°	8
Me ₆ trpn.3CH ₃ I	$N(CH_2CH_2CH_2NMe_2)_3 \cdot 3CH_3I$	solid	288-290		9
trbn	$N((CH_2)_4NH_2)_3 \cdot 4HCl \cdot H_2O$	solid	289-290		9
Me ₆ trbn	$N((CH_2)_4NMe_2)_3 \cdot 4HCl$	solid	291-292		9
TSN	$CH_3C(CH_2NHCH_3)_3$	liquid		38-39 (8mm)	10
TTN	$CH_3C(CH_2N(CH_3)_2)_3$	liquid		49 (5 mm)	10

a. for mixture 90% tren-10% tren, Dow Chem. Co.

2. Complexes

a. First Row Transition Series

(i) Five Coordinate: The preparation of five-coordinate complexes of the first transition series with tripodal amines is extremely straightforward. A solution of the appropriate metal salt in a suitable solvent

is mixed with an equivalent amount or a slight excess of the amine and refluxed for a short time. The reaction is carried out under nitrogen if an oxidizable metal ion, such as Cr²⁺, is used. The complex is isolated by concentration of the solution or addition of a second solvent. Table 2 lists the known five-coordinate compounds.

TABLE 2—FIVE-COORDINATE COMPLEXES OF TRIPODAL AMINES

Compound	Reactants	Solvent	Color	Ref.
[Zn(tren)ClO ₄]ClO ₄	Zn(ClO ₄) ₂ + tren (equimolar)	MeOH.	White (?)	11
[Zn(tren)Br]Br	ZnBr ₂ + tren	EtOH : hexane to ppt	White	11
[Zn(tren)Cl]Cl	ZnCl ₂ + tren	EtOH : hexane to ppt	White	11
[Zn(tren)I]I	ZnI ₂ + tren	EtOH : hexane to ppt	White	11
tren(ZnCl ₂) ₂	ZnCl ₂ (excess) + tren	EtOH	White	11
tren(ZnBr ₂) ₂	ZnBr ₂ (excess) + tren	EtOH	White	11
tren(ZnI ₂) ₂	ZnI ₂ (excess) + tren	EtOH	White	11
[tren ZnCl]Bφ ₄	tren ZnCl ₂ + NaB(φ) ₄ (excess)	EtOH	White (?)	11
[tren ZnBr]Bφ ₄	tren ZnBr ₂ + NaB(φ) ₄ (excess)	EtOH	White (?)	11
[tren ZnI]Bφ ₄	tren ZnI ₂ + NaB(φ) ₄ (excess)	EtOH	White (?)	11
[tren ZnCl]ClO ₄	tren ZnCl ₂ + AgClO ₄ ·H ₂ O	MeOH	White	11
[Zn(tren)(NCS)](SCN)	—	—	White	12
[Zn(Me ₆ tren)Br]Br	ZnBr ₂ + Me ₆ tren	butanol : pet. ether to ppt	White	13
[Zn(Me ₆ tren)I]I	ZnI ₂ + Me ₆ tren	butanol : pet. ether to ppt	White	13
Zn(TSN)Cl ₂	ZnCl ₂ + TSN	EtOH	White	10
Zn(TSN)Br ₂	ZnBr ₂ + TSN	EtOH	White	10
[Co(trpn)ClO ₄]ClO ₄	Co(ClO ₄) ₂ + trpn	boiling EtOH under N ₂	Purple	14
[Co(trpn)Cl]Cl	CoCl ₂ + trpn	boiling EtOH under N ₂	Purple	14
[Co(trpn)Br]Br	CoBr ₂ + trpn	boiling EtOH under N ₂	Purple	14
[Co(trpn)I]I	CoI ₂ + trpn	boiling EtOH under N ₂	Purple	14
[Co(tren)I]I	tren.3HCl + NaOH + CoI ₂	boiling EtOH under N ₂	Blue	15
[Co(tren)NCS]NCS	tren.3HCl + NaOH + Co(SCN) ₂	EtOH under N ₂	Olive-green	15
[Co(Me ₆ trpn)Cl]Bφ ₄	Me ₆ trpn + CoCl ₂ + NaBφ ₄	butan-1-ol under N ₂	Violet	16
[Co(Me ₆ trpn)Br]Bφ ₄	Me ₆ trpn + CoBr ₂ + NaBφ ₄	butan-1-ol under N ₂	Blueviolet	16
[Co(Me ₆ trpn)I]Bφ ₄	Me ₆ trpn + CoI ₂ + NaBφ ₄	butan-1-ol under N ₂	Blueviolet	16
[Co(Me ₆ trpn)I]Bφ ₄	Me ₆ trpn + Co(NCS) ₂ + NaBφ ₄	butan-1-ol under N ₂	Magenta	16
[Co(Me ₆ tren)Cl]Cl	CoCl ₂ + Me ₆ tren (?)	?	?	17
[Co(Me ₆ tren)Br]Br	CoBr ₂ + Me ₆ tren (?)	?	?	17
[Co(Me ₆ tren)I]I	CoI ₂ + Me ₆ tren (?)	?	?	17
[Co(Me ₆ tren)(NCS)]NCS	Co(NCS) ₂ + Me ₆ tren (?)	?	?	7
[Co(Et ₆ tren)Br]Bφ ₄	CoBr ₂ + Et ₆ tren		Purple	18
[Cr(Me ₆ tren)Br]Br	CrBr ₂ + Me ₆ tren	butanol + N ₂ (under)	Pale Sky-blue	19
[Ni(Et ₆ tren)Br]Bφ ₄	NiBr ₂ + Et ₆ tren	?	Orange-brown	
[Ni(Me ₆ trpn)Cl]Bφ ₄	NiCl ₂ + Me ₆ trpn + NaBφ ₄		Purple	16

(Cont.)

Table 2—(Continued)

Compound	Reactants	Solvent	Color	Ref.
[Ni(Me ₆ trpn)Br]Bφ ₄	NiBr ₂ + Me ₆ trpn + NaBφ ₄		Purple	16
[Ni(Me ₆ trpn)I]Bφ ₄	NiI ₂ + Me ₆ trpn + NaBφ ₄		Purple	16
[Ni(Me ₆ tren)(NCS)] SCN.H ₂ O	Ni(NCS) ₂ + Me ₆ tren		Green	20
[Ni(Me ₆ tren)Cl]Cl	NiCl ₂ + Me ₆ tren (?)		?	17
[Ni(Me ₆ tren)Br]Br	NiBr ₂ + Me ₆ tren (?)		?	17
[Ni(Me ₆ tren)NO ₂](NO ₂)	Ni(NO ₂) ₂ + Me ₆ tren (?)		?	17
[Mn(Me ₆ tren)Br]Br	MnBr ₂ + Me ₆ tren	butanol	Greenish-white	17
[Mn(Me ₆ tren)I]I	MnI ₂ + Me ₆ tren	butanol	Green	17
[Fe(Me ₆ tren)Br]Br	FeBr ₂ + Me ₆ tren	butanol	White	17
[Cu(tren)(NCS)](SCN)	tren.3HCl + CuCl ₂ .2H ₂ O + KSCN	H ₂ O	Deep-blue	21
<i>Four-Coordinate</i>				
Zn(TTN)Cl ₂	ZnCl ₂ + TTN	EtOH	White	10
Zn(TTN)Br ₂	ZnBr ₂ + TTN	EtOH	White	10
[Co(Me ₆ trpn)](Bφ ₄) ₂	Co(NCS) ₂ + trpn + NaBφ ₄	butanol	Magenta	16

(ii) Six-Coordinate : At the present time, a large number of six-coordinate tripodal amine complexes have been synthesized and characterized for Co(III) and Cr(III), although some complexes have been made with Ni(II), Rh(III), and other platinum metals.

Cobalt(III) : Co(III)-tren complexes cannot be synthesized by the oxidation of a solution containing a cobalt(II) salt and the amine ligand. ([Co(tren)(NO₂)₂]Cl is the one known exception.) The tren ligand can be introduced into the coordination sphere most easily by the replacement of ammonia, which leaves as a gas.

Long reflux times are necessary to completely eliminate the ammonia. In many cases, the carbonato com-

plex is not isolated, but an appropriate acid is added to the solution to replace the carbonato group. The dichloro, dibromo, diacetato, difluoro and oxalato complexes have been synthesized in this manner.^{22,23,24,25}

The dichloro and hydroxoquo species have also been used as starting materials in the preparation of other tren complexes⁵.

The complex [Co(tren)(NO₂)₂]Cl has been synthesized by the oxidation of CoCl₂.6H₂O in the presence of tren and NaNO₂. The mechanism of this reaction should be of interest, as it is puzzling why this complex is the only Co(III)-tren complex which can be prepared by oxidation.

No six-coordinate cobalt(III) complexes of other tripodal amines are known at the present time.

Table 3 lists the known Co(III)-tren complexes.

TABLE 3—SIX-COORDINATE Co(III)-TREN COMPLEXES

Compound	Starting materials	Color	Ref.
[Co(tren)Cl ₂]Cl.0.5H ₂ O	[Co(NH ₃) ₄ CO ₃]NO ₃ .0.5H ₂ O + tren.3HCl C	Deep purple	22,23
[Co(tren)Cl ₂]Cl.H ₂ O	+ LiOH → then HCl	Blue purple	5
[Co(tren)Cl ₂]ClO ₄	[Co(tren)(NO ₂) ₂]Cl + HCl	Deep blue	22
[Co(tren)ClH ₂ O]SO ₄	[Co(tren)Cl ₂]Cl.0.5H ₂ O + NaClO ₄	Red-violet	22
[Co(tren)Br ₂]Br	[Co(tren)Cl ₂]ClO ₄ + (NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	Green	24
	[Co(NH ₃) ₄ CO ₃]NO ₃ .0.5H ₂ O + tren.3HCl C		
	+ LiOH → then HBr		
[Co(tren)H ₂ OBr]ClO ₄ Br	reflux [Co(tren)CO ₃]ClO ₄ .H ₂ O + HBr → NaClO ₄	Purple	27
[Co(tren)F ₂]ClO ₄ .H ₂ O	[Co(tren)CO ₃]ClO ₄ .H ₂ O + HF (g) in ether	Red-purple	25
[Co(tren)BrCl]Br	[Co(tren)ClSO ₄] + BaBr ₂ + heat	Greenish-blue	26
[Co(tren)FNO ₂]ClO ₄	[Co(tren)F ₂]ClO ₄ + NaNO ₂ + NaClO ₄	Dark orange	26
[Co(tren)ClNO ₂]ClO ₄	[Co(tren)Cl ₂]ClO ₄ + NaNO ₂ + NaClO ₄	Deep orange	26
[Co(tren-d ₈)Cl ₂]ClO ₄	[Co(tren)Cl ₂]Cl + NaOH + D ₂ O	Purple	28
[Co(tren-d ₈)Br ₂]Br	[Co(tren-d ₈)Br ₂]Br + NaOH + D ₂ O	Deep green	28
[Co(tren)(CH ₃ CO ₂) ₂]ClO ₄	[Co(tren)CO ₃]ClO ₄ .H ₂ O + CH ₃ COOH	Red	28
[Co(tren)(CF ₃ CO ₂) ₂]ClO ₄	[Co(tren)CO ₃]ClO ₄ .H ₂ O + CF ₃ CO ₂ H + NaClO ₄	Red	28
[Co(tren)(CH ₃ ClCO ₂) ₂]ClO ₄	[Co(tren)CO ₃]ClO ₄ .H ₂ O + CH ₃ ClCO ₂ H + NaClO ₄	Red	28
[Co(tren)(CHCl ₂ CO ₂) ₂]ClO ₄	[Co(tren)CO ₃]ClO ₄ .H ₂ O + CHCl ₂ CO ₂ H + NaClO ₄	Red	28
[Co(tren)(CCl ₂ CO ₂) ₂]ClO ₄	[Co(tren)CO ₃]ClO ₄ .H ₂ O + CCl ₂ CO ₂ H + NaClO ₄	Red	28

(Contd.)

TABLE 4—SIX-COORDINATE Cr(III) and Ti(III)-tren COMPLEXES

Compound	Starting materials	Color	Ref.
[Cr(tren)Cl ₂]Cl	[Cr(H ₂ O) ₄ Cl ₂]Cl·2H ₂ O + DMSO $\xrightarrow[\text{boil}]{\Delta}$ then add tren	Deep purple	33a
[Cr(tren)ClClO ₄] ₂ ·ClO ₄ ·H ₂ O	[Cr(tren)Cl ₂]Cl + dropwise add 70% HClO ₄ then 2–3 days in refrigerator	Rose-pink	33a
[Cr(tren)ClHSO ₄] ₂ ·H ₂ O	[Cr(tren)Cl ₂]Cl + 18M H ₂ SO ₄ (10–12 drops) and stirring	Rose-pink	33a
[Cr(tren)ox]ClO ₄ ·H ₂ O ^a	[Cr(tren)Cl ₂]Cl (in min. H ₂ O) + Na ₂ C ₂ O ₄ ·H ₂ O $\xrightarrow[\text{slight}]{\Delta}$ decant + NaClO ₄	Red	33a
[Cr(tren)(N ₃) ₂]Br	[Excess NaN ₃ + [Cr(tren)Cl ₂]Cl] $\xrightarrow[\text{steam-bath}]{\Delta}$ + NaBr	Magenta	33a
[Cr(tren)ClSCN]Cl	[Cr(tren)Cl ₂]Cl (in min. H ₂ O) + NaSCN $\xrightarrow[\text{steam-bath}]{\Delta}$ 30 min.	Red	33a
[Cr(tren)ClBr]Br	Same procedure but add NaBr $\xrightarrow[\text{steam-bath}]{\Delta}$ then ethanol		
[Cr(tren)ClSeCN]SeCN	(Cr(tren)Cl ₂]Cl in cold 40% HBr + equal vol. cold C ₂ H ₅ OH [KSeCN + [Cr(tren)Cl ₂]Cl dissolved in 5 ml H ₂ O $\xrightarrow[\text{steam-bath}]{\Delta}$ 30 min. filtered, evap.	Purple Red-brown	33a
[Cr(tren)F ₂]ClO ₄	[Cr(py) ₄ F ₂]ClO ₄ + tren in 2-methoxyethanol + absolute ethanol	Red-violet	31
[Cr(tren)FH ₂ O](ClO ₄) ₂	Method used for [Cr(tren)ClClO ₄]ClO ₄ ·H ₂ O but starting with [Cr(tren)F ₂]ClO ₄ instead of [Cr(tren)Cl ₂]Cl	Rose-pink	33a
[Cr(tren)FSCN]ClO ₄	[Cr(tren)F ₂]ClO ₄ + NaSCN $\xrightarrow[\text{min. H}_2\text{O}]{\text{Steam}}$ 30 minutes and evaporation	Red	33a
Cr(tren)FBr]ClO ₄	Shaking [Cr(tren)FH ₂ O](ClO ₄) ₂ in 20 ml of anhy. methanol + appropriate ammonium or sodium salt, sometimes heat was needed	Purple	33a
[Cr(tren)FC]ClO ₄	same	Purple	33a
[Cr(tren)FN ₃]ClO ₄	same	Purple	33a
[Cr(tren)FAC]ClO ₄ ^b	same	Pink	33a
CrCl ₃ ·(tren) ^c	Tren + CrCl ₃ ·2NMe ₃ (3.7 mmol) (3.8 mmol)	Bluish-grey	33e
[Cr(tren) ₂]Cl ₃ ^c	Tren + CrCl ₃ ·2NMe ₃ (14.6 mmol) (6.2 mmol)	Pink (hygroscopic)	33e
TiCl ₃ (tren) ^c	Tren + TiCl ₃ ·2NMe ₃ (6.4 mmol) (6.9 mmol)	Green (airsensitive)	33e
[Ti(tren) ₂]Cl ₃ ^c	Tren + TiCl ₃ ·2NMe ₃ (10.5 mmol) (4.9 mmol)	Yellow (airsensitive)	33e

a. ox=oxalate b. Ac=acetate c. for IR and electronic spectral data see reference 33e.

TABLE 5—TREN COMPLEXES OF Pt AND Pd

Complex	Starting materials	Color
[Pt(tren)Cl ₂]Cl ₂ ^{a, b}	tren·3HCl + PtCl ₄	Orange
[Pt(tren)Cl ₂]I ₂ ^{a, b}	[Pt(tren)Cl ₂]Cl ₂ + KI	Deep-red
[Pt(tren)Cl ₂][PtCl ₆] ₂ ·2H ₂ O ^a	Pt(tren)Cl ₂]Cl ₂ + H ₂ PtCl ₆	Orange-grown
[Pt(tren)Cl ₂][Pt(CN) ₄] ^{a, b}	[Pt(tren)Cl ₂]Cl ₂ + K ₂ Pt(CN) ₆	White to pale yellow
[Pt(tren)][PtCl ₄] ^a	tren·3HCl + NaOH + K ₂ PtCl ₆	Pale pink
[Pt(tren)] ₂ ·2H ₂ O ^c	tren·3HCl + NaOH + K ₂ PtCl ₆ + KI	White
Pt(tren)I ₂ ^c	Pt(tren)I ₂ ·2H ₂ O + P ₂ O ₅	Cream
Pd(tren)I ₂ ^{a, c}	tren·3HCl + NaOH + PdCl ₂	Cream

a. C, H, metal anal. b. Ionic and coord. Cl c. I d. Pt

TABLE 6a—COMPOUNDS OF TREN TRIHYDROCHLORIDE WITH SOME METAL CHLORIDES

Compound	Starting materials	Color
(1) $N(C_2H_4NH_2)_3 \cdot 3HCl \cdot 3AuCl_3$	$tren \cdot 3HCl + KAuCl_4 \xrightarrow{H_2O} HCl$	Gold
(2) $N(C_2H_4NH_2)_3 \cdot 4HCl \cdot 2AuCl_3$	$tren \cdot 3HCl + HAuCl_4 \cdot 3H_2O \xrightarrow{HCl}$	Pale yellow
(3) $N(C_2H_4NH_2)_3 \cdot 3HCl \cdot 5HgCl_2$	$tren \cdot 3HCl + HgCl_2$ (satd. solu)	Colorless Needles
(4) $2N(C_2H_4NH_2)_3 \cdot 6HCl \cdot 3RhCl_3 \cdot 6H_2O^a$	$tren \cdot 3HCl + Na_3RhCl_6 \cdot 9H_2O$ boil	Salmon-pink crystals
(5) $N(C_2H_4NH_2)_3 \cdot 4HCl \cdot 2AuCl_3$	$(1) + H_2O \longrightarrow$	Yellow-grey
(6) $N(C_2H_4NH_2)_3 \cdot 4HCl \cdot 2RuCl_3 \cdot 2H_2O$	$tren \cdot 3HCl + RuCl_3 \xrightarrow{HCl}$	Reddish-brown
(7) $2N(C_2H_4NH_2)_3 \cdot 6HCl \cdot 3PtCl_2 \cdot 3H_2O$	$tren \cdot 3HCl + Ag_2PtCl_6$ (?)	Pink
(8) $2N(C_2H_4NH_2)_3 \cdot 6HCl \cdot 3PtCl_4 \cdot 10H_2O$	$tren \cdot 3HCl + Na_2PtCl_6 \cdot 6H_2O$	Orange needles

TABLE 6b—COMPOUNDS OF TREN TRIHYDROCHLORIDE WITH RUTHENIUM, RHODIUM AND IRIIDIUM CHLORIDES

Compound	Starting materials	Color	Ref.
$[N(CH_2CH_2NH_2)_3][RuCl_6] \cdot HCl \cdot 2H_2O^a$	$K_3[Ru(Ox)_3] \cdot 4H_2O + HCl +$ $tren \cdot 3HCl \xrightarrow[15-20 \text{ min}]{\text{steam-bath}}$	Reddish brown	33c
$[N(CH_2CH_2NH_2)_3][RuBr_6] \cdot HBr^b$	same—used HBr (9M) instead of HCl	Dark brown	33c
$[N(CH_2CH_2NH_2)_3][RhCl_6] \cdot H_2O^b$	$RhCl_3 \cdot 3H_2O + 6MHCl \xrightarrow[\text{bath}]{\text{steam-}} + tren \cdot 3 Cl$	Red-brown	33d
$[N(CH_2CH_2NH_2)_3][RhCl_6Br_3] \cdot H_2O^b$	same method. Appropriate acid or metal halide	Light green	33d
$[N(CH_2CH_2NH_2)_3][RhCl_6I_3] \cdot H_2O^b$	same method	Deep brown	33d
$[N(CH_2CH_2NH_2)_3][IrCl_6] \cdot 3H_2O^b$	same method	Light green	33d
$[N(CH_2CH_2NH_2)_3][RhBr_6] \cdot 3H_2O^b$	Adding appropriate amt. of $tren \cdot 3HCl$ to a soln. of $K_3Rh(C_2O_4)_3$ (hydrous) in 9M HBr	Red-brown	33d
$[N(CH_2CH_2NH_2)_3][IrBr_6] \cdot H_2O^b$	same but used $K_3Ir(C_2O_4)_3$	Lime-green	33d

a. For Electronic spectral data see reference 33c;

b. for Electronic spectral data see reference 33d.

$(Co(Me_6trpn)(B\phi_4)_2)$ (magenta crystals) which is thought to be fourcoordinate, has been prepared by the reaction of $Co(NCS)_2$, trpn and $NaB\phi_4$ in butanol¹⁶. (Table 2)

c. Lanthanides

Recently the first coordination compounds of the lanthanides with tren have been prepared⁶. The complexes were prepared by direct reaction of the lanthanide salt with tren in an inert atmosphere. Monochelates of the general formula $[Ln(tren)(NO_3)_3]$, where $Ln=La, Pr, Nd, Sm, Gd, Dy, Er$ and Yb , were prepared using 1:1 mole ratio of ligand to metal, salt, while bis chelates of the formula $[Ln(tren)_2NO_3](NO_3)_2$ are obtained for the larger lanthanides La, Pr and Nd , while the six other complexes have no coordinated nitrate, and are formulated $[Ln(tren)_2](NO_3)_3$ where $Ln=Sm, Eu, Gd, Dy, Er$ and Yb . The assignment of coordination number in these complexes was made by elemental analysis and consideration of nitrate absorbances of two possible symmetry types, D_{3h} (free nitrate) and C_{2v} (coordinated nitrate).

C. Spectra and Structure of Complexes

1. Infrared

The infrared spectra of tren and related complexes are quite complicated in the region 800–4000 cm^{-1} ,

and no spectra at lower frequencies have been reported. Such low-frequency studies would be of interest, however, in the study of the metal-nitrogen bonds in these complexes.

In metal-tren complexes, which are the only tripodal amine species for which any infrared spectra have been reported, there are four main absorption regions associated with the N-H bond. These occur at $\sim 3300, \sim 1600, \sim 1300,$ and $\sim 800 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and have been assigned to N-H stretching, antisymmetric deformation, symmetric deformation, and NH_2 rocking, respectively^{26, 27}. Tables 7a, 7b and 7c list some reported bands for metal-tren complexes.

It has been concluded that in six-coordinate cobalt (II)-amine complexes with simple anions, such as chloride, bromide, etc., *cis* isomers have the CH_2 rocking frequency in the region 850–900 cm^{-1} split into two bands. The split band in this region has been used to assign a *cis*-configuration to all of the six-coordinate Co(II)-tren complexes which have been prepared at the present time.

In the region 600–380 cm^{-1} , chromium(III)-tren complexes show a pattern of five absorption bands 570–550 cm^{-1} (I), $\sim 510 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (II), $\sim 470 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (III), 450–440 cm^{-1} (IV), and 410–395 cm^{-1} (V). The location

TABLE 7a—INFRARED FREQUENCIES (cm⁻¹) FOR METAL-TREN COMPLEXES

Complex	NH (stretch)	NH (bend)	CH ₃ (rock)	N-CH ₃ (stretch)	Ref
Zn(tren)(ClO ₄) ₂	3356 s 3300 s	1584 s	875 ms		23
[Zn(tren)Cl]ClO ₄	3344 s 3311 s 3268 s 3236 s 3164 s	1607 ms 1590 s	885 ms		23
[Zn(tren)Cl]Cl	3226 s,b 3145 s	1595 ms,b	880 ms		23
[Zn(tren)Br]Br	3236 s 3144 m	1597 ms	882 ms		23
[Zn(tren)I]I	3257 s b 3145 m	1580 m	879 ms		23
tren(ZnCl ₂) ₂	3300 s 3257 s	1629 w 1590 m 1577 m	880 ms		23
tren(ZnBr ₂) ₂	3300 s 3236 s	1613 w 1575 ms	879 ms		23
tren(ZnI ₂) ₂ ·C ₂ H ₅ OH	3279 ms 3226 ms	1595 s,b	882 ms 873 ms		23 23
tren ZnBrB(C ₆ H ₅) ₄	3289 ms 3247 ms	1589 s	882 ms		23
tren ZnClB(C ₆ H ₅) ₄	3289 ms 3257 ms	1582 s	884 ms		23
tren ZnIB(C ₆ H ₅) ₄	3300 ms 3247 ms	1585 s	885 ms		23
TSNZnCl ₂	3200 s 3300 m 3400 m			2800-3000 s	23
TSNZnBr ₂	3200 s 3300 m 3400 m			2800-3000 s	23
TTNZnCl ₂				2750-3110 (6pKs) s	23
TTNZnBr ₂				2750-3110 (6pKs) s	23
TTN				2750-2880 (3) s	23
TSN				2750-2889 (3) s	33d
tren	3360 3310 3220				6
Ln(tren)(NO ₃) ₃	3320 3310 3300 3270 s 3170				6
[Ln(tren) ₂ NO ₃](NO ₃) ₃	3320 3300 3260 3190				6
[Ln(tren) ₂](NO ₃) ₃	3250 s 3140				6

vs-very strong ; s-strong , ms-medium strong ; w-weak ; b-broad ; pKs-peaks.

TABLE 7b—INFRARED FREQUENCIES (cm⁻¹) FOR DEUTERATED AND NON-DEUTERATED 28 COBALT (III)-TREN COMPLEXES

Complex	NH- (N-D) stretch	N-H(N-D) antisym bend	N-H(N-D) sym bend	NH ₂ (ND ₂) rock	NH ₂ (ND ₂) twist	NH(N-D) wag	CH ₂ rock
[Co(tren)Cl ₃]Cl.0.5H ₂ O	3330 s 3310 w 3241 s 3180 s,b 3078 s	1605 m 1590 m	1315 m 1295 sh	790 m	1035 m 1008 s	1168 m 1151 m	900 m 865 m 854 m
[Co(tren-d ₆)Cl ₃]Cl.0.5H ₂ O	2480 s 2475 w 2430 s 2378 s 2281 s 3310 s	1182 m 1178 sh	1065 (?)	570 m	870 m 840 m 830 m	958 m 945 m	
[Co(tren)Br ₃]Br	3239 s 3140 sh 3098 s 3065 s	1602 s 1578 s	1310 m 1290 sh	790 m	1022 w 999 s 980 m	1140 s 1138 s	892 m 852 m
[Co(tren-d ₆)Br ₃]Br	2475 m 2430 s 2380 sh 2300 s 2275 s	1175 sh 1165 m	? ?	565 m (?)	861 m 834 m 820 m	958 s 940 m	
[Co(tren)(CH ₃ CO ₂) ₃]ClO ₄	3330 s 3295 s 3238 sh 3145 s		1320 sh 1295 sh	790 m	998 m 981 m		900 m 870 m 860 w
[Co(tren)(CH ₃ ClCO ₂) ₃]ClO ₄	3050 m 3330 s 3308 s 3278 sh 3145 s	1590 m	1320 m 1300 sh	790 m	1035 s 995 m 979 m		900 m 865 m 858 m
[Co(tren)CHCl ₂ CO ₂) ₃]ClO ₄	3080 m 3310 s 3260 s 3205 m 3140 s	1610 m 1595 m	1318 m 1297 sh	790 m	1033 s 1005 m 991 m		900 870 m 860 m
[Co(tren)(CCl ₂ CO ₂) ₃]ClO ₄	3078 m 3320 m 3280 s 3240 m	1610 m 1590 m			1035 sh 990 m 979 m		900 m
[Co(tren)(CH ₂ BrCO ₂) ₃]ClO ₄	3180 m 3305 s 3290 s 3210 sh 3130 m 3050 m	1605 sh	1330 sh 1305 sh	790 m	1038 s 1000 m 985 m		900 m 870 m
[Co(tren)(CHBr ₂ CO ₂) ₃]ClO ₄	3310 s 3260 s 3210 m 3150 m 3080 m	1610 sh 1590 m	1320 sh 1300 sh	795 m	1035 s 1005 m 995 m		900 m 870 m 863 m
[Co(tren)(CBr ₃ CO ₂) ₃]ClO ₄	3321 s 3310 s 3270 s 3130 m,b	1615 m 1585 m		810 m	1038 sh 990 m 980 m		900 m 870 m 863 m
[Co(tren)(CF ₃ CO ₂) ₃]ClO ₄	3320 s 3280 sh 3160 m 3140 m	1620 m 1595 m	1328 w 1315 w 1310 w	790 s	1035 s 100 sm 989 m		900 m

vs - very strong
s - strong
ms - medium strong
w - weak
b - broad

of absorbances for each complex is listed in Table 7c. A similar pattern, with slightly shifted wave numbers, has been found in the region for *cis*-bis ethylenediamine complexes of chromium(III)^{33f}. For these complexes, there was no one absorption corresponding to a pure chromium-nitrogen stretching vibration as all chromium-nitrogen vibrations were strongly coupled to vibrations of the ethylenediamine ring. This coupling was attributed to the low symmetry of the *cis*-complexes, and the situation is likely to be similar in the necessarily *cis* tren complexes.

The carbon-nitrogen stretching vibrations in the selenocyanate complex were in the region expected for coordination through nitrogen (~ca, 2080 cm⁻¹, 2075 cm⁻¹), and this mode of coordination has been found for other selenocyanate complexes of first-row transition elements.

The absorptions in the 3550-3200 cm⁻¹ and 1650-1620 cm⁻¹ regions in the complexes containing water of hydration were attributed to the antisymmetric and symmetric O-H stretching modes and to the H-O-H bending modes, respectively.

The infrared spectra of the salts [N(CH₂CH₂NH₂)₃]₂[RuCl₆].HCl.2H₂O(I) and [N(CH₂CH₂NH₂)₃]₂[RuBr₆].HBr(II) reported by Gaylor and Senoff^{33g} show absorption bands due to the cation, N(CH₂CH₂NH₂)₃³⁺ and additional bands at 3600(s), 3400(s), and 1630(m) cm⁻¹ which are characteristic of water of crystallization in I and are absent in II. These are strong, sharp bands at 313 and 240 cm⁻¹ for salts I and II, respectively which are assigned to the infrared active F_{1u} modes; ν_{Ru-Cl} and ν_{Ru-Br}, respectively, and support an octahedral environment around ruthenium(III).

Table 8 lists the band assignments of several new hexahalo complexes of the formulae [N(CH₂CH₂NH₂)₃]₂[MX₆] (M = Rh, Ir; X = Cl, Br) and [N(CH₂CH₂NH₂)₃]₂[RhCl₅Y] (Y = Br, I). The rather complicated spectra of these complexes were examined for four main features^{33d}: (a) lattice water vibrations (3400-3500 and ~1630 cm⁻¹); (b) N-H stretching vibrations (2950-3100 cm⁻¹); (c) N-H anti-symmetric bending vibrations (~1550-1650 cm⁻¹); and (d) M-X stretching vibrations (<400 cm⁻¹).

TABLE 7c—INFRARED SPECTRA OF CHROMIUM(III)—TREN COMPLEXES BETWEEN 600—380 cm⁻¹

Bands	Cl ₂]Cl ^a	ClClO ₄]ClO ₄ .H ₂ O	ClHSO ₄]HSO ₄ .H ₂ O	OX]ClO ₄ .H ₂ O ^b	CINCS]Cl ^c	ClBr]Br ^d	CINCSel]NCS
I		570	580		570	570	
		552			565	555	
II		516	505	514	514	505	516
III	487		480	487	492	478	478
	458		470				
IV		450	440		445	430	440
V	400	392	38	400	396	392	392
	378			389			435
	FH ₂ O](ClO ₄) ₂	FNCS]ClO ₄	FBr]ClO ₄	FN ₂]ClO ₄	FAc]ClO ₄	(N ₃) ₂ Br ^e	FC]ClO ₄
I	570	572	530	570	568	570	570
	552	570		550	552	550	500
II	514	505		509	511	507	523
				503	505		509
III	496	480	479	478	478	474	479
IV		438	440	440	440	442	438
V	410	410	410	408	410	392	410
	400	392			392		392
	392						

(a) also 532, 420; (b) also 542, 530; (c) also 422; (d) also 415; (e) also 420

TABLE 8—INFRARED SPECTRAL BAND ASSIGNMENTS FOR RHODIUM(III) AND IRIIDIUM(III) HEXAHALO COMPLEXES

Complex	Lattice water (cm ⁻¹)	N-H sym. stretch (cm ⁻¹)	N-H asym. deformation (cm ⁻¹)	M-X stretch (cm ⁻¹)
[N(CH ₂ CH ₂ NH ₂) ₃] ₂ [RhCl ₆].H ₂ O	3510 m 3380 m 1610-20 br. wk	3060-3160 br	1570 m 1580 sh	330
[N(CH ₂ CH ₂ NH ₂) ₃] ₂ [RhCl ₅ Br].H ₂ O	3510 m 3380 m	3110-3140 br	1595 m 1605 m	355 s 335 w 295 sh
[N(CH ₂ CH ₂ NH ₂) ₃] ₂ [RhCl ₅ I].H ₂ O	3520 m 3360 m	3060-3140 br	1595 m 1605 sh	360 sh 335 w 295 sh
[N(CH ₂ CH ₂ NH ₂) ₃] ₂ [RhBr ₆].3H ₂ O	3500 m 3400 m 1620 wk	3100-3170 br	1550 m 1570 sh	260 s
[N(CH ₂ CH ₂ NH ₂) ₃] ₂ [IrCl ₆].3H ₂ O	3500 m 3380 m 1680 wk	3120-3160 br	1570 m 1560 sh	305 s
[N(CH ₂ CH ₂ NH ₂) ₃] ₂ [IrBr ₆].H ₂ O	3500 m 3380 m	3080-3120 br	1550 m 1560 sh	220 s

s=sharp; sh=shoulder; wk=weak; br=broad; m=medium

The sharp absorptions which are seen below 300 cm^{-1} in the infrared spectra of the hexachloro and hexabromo complexes are assigned to the metal-stretching vibration. This assignment is in agreement with ruthenium (III) salts^{33c}.

2. Electronic Spectra

a. Six-coordinate: The visible spectra of most six-coordinate complexes have not been studied theoretically, but have been measured as an aid in the identification of compounds in synthetic and kinetic studies. Table 9 lists spectral maxima for these complexes, with the ϵ_{max} values and the solvent used (when it was reported). In some cases rapid aquation of the parent complex makes it possible to obtain only the spectra of the aquation products.

Jørgenson³⁸ recorded the spectra of some Ni(II)-tren and Cu(II)-tren complexes and compared them

with those of other polydentate amines. He assigned the four strongest absorption bands in the Ni(II) complexes to transitions from the ground state 3T_2 (F) to 1T_2 (D), 3T_2 (F), 3T_4 (F) and 3T_4 (P), and also calculated oscillator strengths for each band. Because of the similarity of their spectra to those of the bis ethylenediamine species and also because of the facile exchange of water by ammonia, ethylenediamine or glycinate, he concluded that the Ni(II)-tren species have a *cis*-octahedral configuration in solution.

A *cis*-octahedral structure was assigned to the Cu(II)-tren species for the same reasons. It is interesting that [Cu(tren)NCS] NCS has been found to be five-coordinate in the solid state, although no spectra in solutions have been measured. It seems that both five- and six-coordinate Cu(II)-tren complexes can exist and it would be interesting to compare the solution spectra of [Cu(tren) NCS] NCS with those of other Cu(tren)²⁺ complexes.

TABLE 9—ELECTRONIC SPECTRA OF SIX-COORDINATE TREN SPECIES

Complex	Solvent	λ_{nm}	$\epsilon, M^{-1}cm^{-1}$	λ, nm	$\epsilon, M^{-1}cm^{-1}$	Ref.
Co(tren)Cl ₃ ⁺	50% HCl	565	125	390	120	24
Co(tren)Br ₃ ⁺	Nujol Mull	595				39
Co(tren)BrH ₂ O ²⁺	0.1M HClO ₄	555	138	380 sh	143	24
Co(tren)(H ₂ O) ₆ ²⁺	0.1M HClO ₄	505	107	350	99	24
Co(tren)(H ₂ O) ₅ ²⁺	?	507	99.5	360	78.4	40
Co(tren)Br(DMF) ₂ ²⁺	DMF	560	140	390 (sh)	180	39
Co(tren)Br(NMF) ₂ ²⁺	NMF	615	130	440 (sh)	140	39
Co(tren)Br(DMSO) ₂ ²⁺	DMSO	560	140	410-400 (sh)	150	39
Co(tren)(NMF) ₃ ²⁺	NMF	560	110	410-400 (sh)	120	39
Co(tren)(FORM) ₃ ²⁺	FORM	550	110	410-380 (sh)	110	39
Co(tren)CO ₃ ⁺	H ₂ O	504	132	353	110	26
Co(tren)CO ₃ ⁺	Nujol Mull	503		348		26
Co(tren)C ₂ O ₄ ⁺	H ₂ O	497	128	355	136	26
Co(tren)C ₂ O ₄ ⁺	Nujol Mull	494		350		26
Co(tren)BrCl ⁺	Nujol Mull	571				26
Co(tren)F ₃ ⁺	H ₂ O	517	110	363	74	26
Co(tren)F ₃ ⁺	Nujol Mull	516		360		26
Co(tren)ClSO ₄	H ₂ O	537	140	374	95	26
Co(tren)ClSO ₄	Nujol Mull	529		368		26
Co(tren)BrSO ₄	H ₂ O	553	156			26
Co(tren)BrSO ₄	Nujol Mull	540				26
Co(tren)BrClO ₄ ⁺	H ₂ O	554	160			26
Co(tren)BrClO ₄ ⁺	Nujol Mull	543				26
Co(tren)ClH ₂ O ²⁺	H ₂ O	537	140	375	95	26
Co(tren)(NO ₃) ₃ ⁺	H ₂ O	433	238			26
Co(tren)(NO ₃) ₃ ⁺	Nujol Mull	430				26
Co(tren)(N ₃) ₃ ⁺	H ₂ O	525	365			26
Co(tren)(N ₃) ₃ ⁺	Nujol Mull	523				26
Co(tren)(NCS) ₃ ⁺	H ₂ O	495	407			26
Co(tren)(NCS) ₃ ⁺	Nujol Mull	493				26
Co(tren)F(NCS) ⁺	H ₂ O	499	288			26
Co(tren)F(NCS) ⁺	Nujol Mull	497				26
Co(tren)Cl(NCS) ⁺	H ₂ O	536	197			26
Co(tren)Cl(NCS) ⁺	Nujol Mull	535				26
Co(tren)Br(NCS) ⁺	H ₂ O	550	224			26
Co(tren)Br(NCS) ⁺	Nujol Mull	552				26
Co(tren)(CH ₃ CO ₂) ₃ ⁺	H ₂ O-EtOH	510	191	366	114	28
Co(tren)(CH ₃ ClCO ₂) ₃ ⁺	H ₂ O-EtOH	510	189	366	112	28
Co(tren)(CH ₃ Cl ₂ CO ₂) ₃ ⁺	H ₂ O-EtOH	506	184	365	106	28
Co(tren)(CCl ₃ CO ₂) ₃ ⁺	H ₂ O-EtOH	507	170	363	100	28
Co(tren)(CH ₃ BrCO ₂) ₃ ⁺	H ₂ O-EtOH	509	191	365	120	28

(Contd.)

TABLE 9—(continued)

Complex	Solvent	λ_{nm}	$\epsilon, M^{-1}cm^{-1}$	λ, nm	$\epsilon, M^{-1}cm^{-1}$	Ref.
Co(tren)(CHBr ₃ CO ₂) ²⁺	H ₂ O-EtOH	508	186	365	109	28
Co(tren)(CBr ₄ CO ₂) ²⁺	H ₂ O-EtOH	508	192	364	123	28
Co(tren)(CF ₃ CO ₂) ²⁺	H ₂ O-EtOH	502	168	362	100	28
[Co(tren)(gly)] ²⁺	H ₂ O	471	105	342	100	5
[Co(tren)(L-ala)] ²⁺	H ₂ O	471	105	342	91	5
[Co(tren)(D-ala)] ²⁺	H ₂ O	480	111	346	110	5
[Co(tren)(leu)] ²⁺	H ₂ O	471	126	343	118	5
[Co(tren)(val)] ²⁺	H ₂ O	472	124	343	110	5
[Co(tren)(phen)] ²⁺	H ₂ O	471	122	343	115	5
Co(tren)(pro) ²⁺	H ₂ O	476		343		5
Co(tren)(try) ²⁺	H ₂ O	470	118	350		5
Co(tren)(his) ²⁺	H ₂ O	471	119	338	126	5
Co(tren)(ser) ²⁺	H ₂ O	471	118	343	122	5
Co(tren)(thre) ²⁺	H ₂ O	470	110	341	103	5
Co(tren)(cysCH ₃) ²⁺	H ₂ O	470	128	340		5
Co(tren)(cySO ₃) ²⁺	H ₂ O	471	116	343	110	5
Co(tren)(met) ²⁺	H ₂ O	463	161	400		5
Co(tren)(lys) ²⁺	H ₂ O	472	120	343	117	5
Co(tren)(arg) ²⁺	H ₂ O	473		340		5
Co(tren)(asp) ²⁺	H ₂ O	472		344		5
Co(tren)(sar) ²⁺	H ₂ O	477	103	345	108	5
Co(tren)(glyOEt) ²⁺	H ₂ O	514	99	370	102	30
Chromium complexes						
Cr(tren)F ₃ ⁺	H ₂ O	528	116.5	378	56.8	31
Cr(tren)Cl ₃ ⁺	12 M HCl	540	114	408	95.0	33d
Cr(tren)(H ₂ O)Cl ²⁺	H ₂ O	518	71	394	63.0	33d
Cr(tren)ClCl(ClO ₄) ⁺	H ₂ O	508	83	375	36.3	33d
Cr(tren)Cl(NCSe) ⁺	H ₂ O	505	86.3	341	194.0	33d
Cr(tren)Cl(NCS) ⁺	H ₂ O	518	146.0	400	72.5	33d
Cr(tren)(OX) ⁺	H ₂ O	505	90.0	369	66.0	33d
Cr(tren)ClBr ⁺	12 M HCl	556		410	81.5	33d
Cr(tren)(N ₃) ⁺	50% MeOH	529	103	372	90.2	33d
Cr(tren)(H ₂ O)F ²⁺	H ₂ O	521	639	375	32.4	33d
Cr(tren)F(NCS) ⁺	50% MeOH	513	132	369	50.0	33d
Cr(tren)F(CH ₃ COO) ⁺	50% MeOH	515	120	383	52.0	33d
Cr(tren)FBr ⁺	H ₂ O	532	54.1	376	29.5	33d
Cr(tren)FCl ⁺	H ₂ O	515	81.9	394	31.2	33d
Cr(tren)F(N ₃) ⁺	H ₂ O	529	175	402	61.6	33d
Cr(tren)Cl(HSO ₄) ⁺	H ₂ O	524	112	392	69.8	33d
Cr(tren)Cl(H ₂ O) ₂ ²⁺	H ₂ O	543	72	398	45.1	33d
Rhodium complexes						
Rh(tren)Cl ₃ ⁺	0.1 M HClO ₄	364	332	300	294	33b
Rh(tren)Cl(H ₂ O) ²⁺	0.1 M HClO ₄			332	246	33b
Nickel complexes						
Ni(tren)(H ₂ O) ₂ ²⁺	H ₂ O	950	15.5			38
		782	6.3			
		561	9.3			
		360	12.0			
Ni ₂ (tren) ₂ ⁴⁺	H ₂ O excess tren	935	9.4			38
		800	4.6			
		548	7.2			
		348	9.3			
Ni(tren)(NH ₃) ₂ ²⁺	dil NH ₃	910	12.5			38
		784	7.0			
		549	10.1			
		354	13.0			
Ni(tren)en ²⁺	?	910	11.0			38
		800	8.1			
		534	8.8			
		345	14.2			
Ni(tren)(gly) ⁺	?	890	14.0			33
		794	9.8			
		532	11.0			
		354	11.0			
Copper Complexes						
Cu(tren)(H ₂ O) ₂ ²⁺	H ₂ O	860	117			38
Cu(tren)(NH ₃) ₂ ²⁺	NH ₃ (dil)	785	134			38

TABLE 10—ELECTRONIC SPECTRA OF FIVE-COORDINATED TRIPODAL SPECIES

Compound	Medium	λ nm(ϵ m)	Ref.
[Co(trpn)ClO ₄]ClO ₄	reflectance	1552, 856, 550, 496 (sh)	14
[Co(trpn)ClO ₄] ⁺	nitroethane	1546(21), 841(35), 550(230), 507 (sh) (100)	14
[Co(trpn)] ⁺	nitromethane	1589(10), 800(16), 553(230), 498 sh (57)	14
Co(tren) ⁺	nitroethane	1600(50), 800(30), 589(250), 501(120)	14
Co(tren)(OH) ⁺	? alk. soln.	841, 695	41
Co(Me ₆ trpn)Cl ⁺	reflectance	1335 (sh), 1178, 894, 579, 550 (sh)	16
Co(Me ₆ trpn)Cl ⁺	<i>o</i> -diCl benzene	1565(20), 1300(30) 963(25), 629 (sh), 611(195), 569(150)	16
Co(Me ₆ trpn)Br ⁺	reflectance	1352 sh, 1300, 910, 589, 554 sh	16
Co(Me ₆ trpn)Br ⁺	<i>o</i> -diCl benzene	1697(24), 1372(39), 101(34), 626(265), 592 sh	16
Co(Me ₆ trpn) ⁺	reflectance	1389, 1177, 945, 596, 556	16
Co(Me ₆ trpn) ⁺	<i>o</i> -diCl benzene	1726(15), 1389(28), 102(30), 672 sh, 642(145), 611(147), 593 sh	16
Co(tren)(NCS) ⁺	nitroethane	1500(40), 720(30) sh, 600(250), 490(100), 450(90)	15
Cr(Me ₆ tren)Br ⁺	reflectance	920, 800, 400	19
Cr(Me ₆ tren)Br ⁺	dichloromethane	920(85), 800(45), 600(20), 480(20)	19
[Mn(Me ₆ tren)Br]Br	reflectance	650, 474, 452, 402, 375	42
[Mn(Me ₆ tren)Br]Br	CH ₂ Cl	614(4), 472(1.0), 437(1.0), 400 sh, 372(1.2), 360 sh	42
[Mn(Me ₆ tren)]I	reflectance	669, 472, 441, 404, 376 sh	42
[Mn(Me ₆ tren)]I	CH ₂ Cl ₂	625(2.1), 471(4.8), 434(4.8), 401(7.5)	42
[Fe(Me ₆ tren)Br]Br	reflectance	<2500, 1020, 700, 542, 470, 433, 406, 381	42
[Fe(Me ₆ tren)Br]Br	CH ₂ Cl ₂	<2500, 1020(12.0), 695(0.8) 620 sh, 538(8)	42
[Fe(Me ₆ tren)Br]Br	reflectance	472(1.0), 434(1.1), 402(1.3), 382(1.3)	42
[Ni(Me ₆ tren)Cl]Cl	reflectance	1400, 950, 870 sh, 690, 520 sh, 430	17
[Ni(Me ₆ tren)Cl]Cl	CHCl ₃	1400(4), 950(2), 920(1.5), 720(5), 500(6), 420(170)	17
[Ni(Me ₆ tren)NCS]NCS.H ₂ O	solu (?)	1295(35.5), 886(24.4), 801(27.6) 618(34.4), 401(185)	43
<i>Miscellaneous 4-coordinate</i>			
[Co(Me ₆ trpn)](Bφ ₄) ₃	reflectance	1220, 953 sh, 885, 550, 527 sh	16

TABLE 11—PREDICTED AND OBSERVED SPECTRA OF [Co(Me₆ Tren)Cl]Cl AND [Ni(Me₆ Tren)Cl]Cl

Compound	Transitions	Frequencies, cm ⁻¹		Ref.
		calculated	observed	
[Co(Me ₆ tren)Cl]Cl $\mu=1.2$ a.u.	⁴ A ₂ ' (F) → ⁴ E'' (F) ⁴ E' (F) ⁴ A ₂ ' (F) ⁴ E'' (P)	4,000	5,500	19
		12,000	12,500	
		15,800	15,600-16,100	
		20,000	20,000	
[Ni(Me ₆ tren)Cl]Cl $\mu=2.2$ a.u.	³ E' (F) → ³ E'' (F) ³ E' (F) ³ A ₁ '' (F), ³ A ₂ '' (F) ³ E'' (D) ³ E'' (P) ³ A ₂ ' (P)	7,000	7,200	17
		12,900	11,000-12,000	
		14,000		
		15,300	15,000	
		19,000	~20,000 sh	
		23,500	23,500	
		26,000	~25,500 sh	

b. Five-coordinate Complexes: The five coordinate complexes of tren and related ligands with bivalent ions of the first transition series have been of interest because of the relative rarity of this coordination

number, especially in complexes with high spin. The electronic spectra of these complexes, shown in Table 10, have been studied not only as an aid in establishing the geometry of the species but also as a means of

testing ligand field models for five-coordinate geometry. Table II gives the theoretical and predicted transitions for $[\text{Co}(\text{Me}_6\text{trpn})\text{Cl}]\text{Cl}$ and $[\text{Ni}(\text{Me}_6\text{trpn})\text{Cl}]\text{Cl}^{17}$.

The electronic spectra of $[\text{M}(\text{Me}_6\text{trpn})\text{X}]\text{X}$ species where $\text{M} = \text{Co}(\text{II}), \text{Mn}(\text{II}), \text{Fe}(\text{II}),$ and $\text{Cr}(\text{II}), \text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}$ and I , and $\text{Y} = \text{Br}, \text{I}, \text{B}\phi_4,$ and NCS , have been studied extensively and some generalizations can be made :

(1) The reflectance spectra of all the complexes of a given element are similar in shape, with only small shifts in peak frequencies indicative of the position of the halide in the spectrochemical series.

(2) Absorption spectra of the solutions of the complexes in such solvents as $\text{CHCl}_3, \text{EtNO}_2,$ and CH_2Cl_2 are virtually identical with the solid state spectra. This is a good indication that no appreciable structural change occurs on dissolution of the complex.

(3) The spectra of these complexes indicate that they have a five-coordinate trigonal bipyramidal structure, both in the solid state and in solution, with all four nitrogen atoms of the ligand attached to the metal. The three primary amine groups are at the corners of an equilateral triangle, with the tertiary nitrogen and anion at the apexes.

(4) Only five-coordinate complexes are known for the Me_6trpn and Et_6trpn ligands at the present time. It is thought that only three bulky groups can fit in a plane, thus eliminating the possibility of an octahedral or square pyramidal structure. Tren itself, however, forms both five- and six-coordinate complexes with $\text{Co}(\text{II})^{10}$ and perhaps other metal ions. It is thought that tren is on the borderline for five- or six-coordination and that it can have either coordination number depending on the nature of the metal ion and of the other ligands present.

(5) Comparisons have been made between the spectra of Me_6trpn and Me_6tren complexes¹⁶ to see what effect lengthening the "legs" of the tripodal amine would have on the spectra and structure of the complex. Comparisons between the spectra of $[\text{Ni}(\text{Me}_6\text{tren})\text{X}]\text{X}$ and $[\text{Ni}(\text{Me}_6\text{trpn})\text{X}]\text{X}$, $\text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{Br},$ and I , show that they have the same number and shape of absorbance bands with a shift to lower frequencies in the $[\text{Ni}(\text{Me}_6\text{trpn})\text{X}]\text{X}$ species, but that the relative intensities of the corresponding bands are different. It was concluded that the Me_6tren complexes are five-coordinate, but are distorted from regular trigonal bipyramidal symmetry.

(6) The reflectance spectra of $[\text{Co}(\text{Me}_6\text{trpn})\text{X}]\text{B}\phi_4$ complexes are quite different from those of the corresponding Me_6tren series and resemble those of some pseudo tetrahedral $\text{Co}(\text{II})$ species. Tetrahedral distortion is therefore suggested for these complexes, and in fact has been found by x-ray analysis in similar $\text{Co}(\text{II})$ complexes of the tripodal ligand NP_3^{44} . The electronic spectra of these Me_6trpn complexes in

solution differ from those of the solid state and also change with the polarity of the solvent. The spectrum of $[\text{Co}(\text{Me}_6\text{trpn})\text{Br}]\text{B}\phi_4$ in *o*-dichloro benzene resembles that of pseudotetrahedral complexes, while in nitroethane the pattern of bands suggests no definite stereochemistry.¹⁷

3. Nuclear Magnetic Resonance

The use of NMR in the study of these complexes has been limited to two investigations, both quite recent. Forsberg^{6,45} investigated the NMR spectrum of a $\text{tren} : \text{Nd}(\text{ClO}_4)_3$ solution [4 : 1 mole ratio] in deuterated acetonitrile. Methylene proton resonances corresponding to both free (2.65 ppm) and coordinated (3.48 and 7.41 ppm) ligands are observed, indicating slow intermolecular ligand exchange on the NMR time scale. The NH_2 resonance of the free ligand occurs at 1.54 ppm, while that of the coordinated ligand could not be seen. The integrated intensities of the methylene protons of coordinated and free ligands are equal, which it is felt establishes the existence of the $\text{Ln}(\text{tren})_2^{47}$ species in solution.

Some zinc halide complexes of TSN and TTN have been studied by nmr¹⁰. Both TTNZnCl_2 and TTNZnBr_2 show a nine-line spectrum. The zinc ion is interpreted as having a coordination number of four in these species which should result in a seven-line spectrum. The two additional lines come from AB coupling between the two different types of methylene protons on the chelate ring. The coordination geometry of the zinc ion is a slightly distorted tetrahedron, with bidentate co-ordination of TTN to the zinc atom. The chelate ring is thought to adopt a frozen pseudo-chair conformation at room temperature, due to the bulky substituents on the ring. The complexes with TSN show four single absorbances, similar to those of the free ligand. 100 MHz spectra show the hydrogen on the nitrogen split into a triplet with $J_{\text{H-N}} = 53$ cps. From IR and NMR it is concluded that zinc has a coordination number of five in these compounds, which can be considered as distorted trigonal bipyramids or distorted tetragonal pyramids. TSN acts as a tridentate chelating agent, forming three six membered rings. The tridentate behavior of TSN seems to indicate that the ability of a tripodal ligand to chelate is not determined by the presence of an apical coordinating group.

4. X-ray

The first x-ray studies of tripodal amine compounds were carried out in 1935 by Cox and Webster³⁵, who made a brief study of both $[\text{Ni}(\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{NH}_2)_3]_2(\text{NCS})_2$ and $[\text{Ni}(\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{NH}_2)_3] \text{SO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The thiocyanate was found to be orthorhombic with four molecules in the unit cell, which had dimensions $a = 10.79 \text{ \AA}, b = 14.66 \text{ \AA}, c = 8.59 \text{ \AA}$, and density 1.55 g/cc . The sulfate was monoclinic with $a = 18.4 \text{ \AA}, b = 10.03 \text{ \AA}, c = 10.28 \text{ \AA}$, and four molecules also in the unit cell. Both substances were asymmetric. Atomic positions could not be determined from these data. In 1958 Hall and Wolfe⁴⁶ found essentially the same cell dimensions for the thiocyanate, and using Patterson projections, found that the thiocyanates were in *cis* positions and were coordinated through the nitrogen.

Rasmussen³⁴ made a thorough crystal structure determination on Ni(tren)(NCS)₂. A parallel projection of this molecule, along with pertinent crystal data, is given in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Parallel projection of the Ni tren molecule. Unit cell $a=10.82$, $b=14.71$, $c=8.62 \text{ \AA}$. Space group: $P2_1 2_1 2$, No. 19 (D_2)⁴ 4 molecules in unit cell.

The three chelate rings are nonplanar, in contrast to the tren trihydrochloride molecule, which has C_3 symmetry⁴⁷. Only the ring $N_5-C_6-C_5-N_3$ has normal bond distances. The N_1-Ni-N_2 angle of 152° shows the considerable distortion of coordinated tren, with N_1 and N_2 drawn away from the thiocyanate ligands. The rather long bond lengths for N_5-C_3 (1.68 \AA) and for C_2-C_1 (1.66) are most likely due to steric strain in the coordinated tren molecule.

Cox and Webster⁵⁵ made a brief study of $[\text{NiN}(\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{NH}_2)_3](\text{NCS})_2$. This salt forms monoclinic plates, with cell dimensions $a=14.78$, $b=14.57$, $c=7.54 \text{ \AA}$ and four molecules to the unit cell. A detailed crystal structure determination on this compound would be of interest so that the effect of lengthening the "legs" of the tripodal amine on bond lengths and angles could be seen.

Several x-ray studies have been made on five-coordinate tren complexes containing thiocyanate groups. Basolo¹¹ found that $\text{Cu}(\text{tren})(\text{NCS})_2$ had orthorhombic symmetry, space group $P2_1 2_1 2$, and cell dimensions $a=11.16$, $b=14.16$, and $c=9.11 \text{ \AA}$. On the basis of the similarity of this compound in cell dimensions and space group to $\text{Ni}(\text{tren})(\text{NCS})_2$, and also because of the IR spectrum (two C-N frequencies at 2094 and 2060 cm^{-1} and two C-S frequencies at 818 and 745 cm^{-1}), it was suggested that the copper compound was *cis*-octahedral with one thiocyanate N-bonded and one S-bonded. Jain and Lingafelter⁴⁸ redetermined the structure and found that the copper was surrounded by five nitrogen atoms in a distorted trigonal bipyramid. Bond lengths showed that one thiocyanate was not coordinated to the copper. $[\text{Zn}(\text{tren})(\text{NCS})] \text{NCS}$ has also been found to be a slightly distorted trigonal bipyramid with one ionic thiocyanate¹².

A three-dimensional x-ray study of $[\text{Co}(\text{Me}_6\text{tren})\text{Br}]\text{Br}$ has been carried out by DiVaara and Orioli⁴⁹. The crystals are cubic and of space group $P2_1 3$ with

$a=12.088 \text{ \AA}$. The complex has a trigonal bipyramidal structure of C_3 symmetry, and bond lengths of the ligand molecule are normal. This complex is the first five-coordinate $\text{Co}(\text{II})$ complex having a trigonal bipyramidal structure with C_3 symmetry, and it is felt that the symmetry of the complex cation is determined by the particular shape of the ligand molecule.

5. Isomerism

Geometrical isomers resulting from the controlled configuration of a tripodal ligand such as tren are theoretically possible in an octahedral complex. In a complex $\text{M}(\text{tren})\text{XY}^{n+}$, where X and Y are two different monodentate ligands or two different donor atoms from a bidentate chelating agent, each could be *cis* or *trans* to the tertiary nitrogen of the amine ligand. The $\text{Co}(\text{III})$ -tren complexes are the only species in which the possibility of this isomerism has been investigated.

The first evidence of isomers was found by Collman⁵ who reacted amino acids with $\text{Co}(\text{tren})(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})^{2+}$ to form the species $\text{Co}(\text{tren})(\text{AA})$, where A is the amino acid nitrogen and A' the oxygen from carboxylate. Treatment of $\text{Co}(\text{tren})(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})^{2+}$ with glycine ethylester at $\text{pH } 7.5-8.0$ gave an orange and a red crystalline compound. Elemental analyses and NMR data confirmed that two isomeric glycinate complexes were formed. The complexes were separated by fractional crystallization and were found to have slightly different electronic spectra (orange complex- λ_{max} 472 nm ($\epsilon_m=105$), λ_{max} 342 nm ($\epsilon_m=100$) and red complex λ_{max} 499 nm ($\epsilon_m=92$), λ_{max} 347 nm ($\epsilon_m=75$)). The orange complex was identical with the one obtained by the reaction of $\text{Co}(\text{tren})(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})^{2+}$ with glycine.

The same workers allowed $\text{Co}(\text{tren})\text{Cl}_2^+$ to undergo the primary acid hydrolysis before reaction with glycine ethyl ester. An intermediate containing the amino acid ester as a monodentate ligand coordinated through the nitrogen was isolated and characterized. Hydrolysis of this intermediate gave an orange glycinate complex identical to the one formed from $\text{Co}(\text{tren})(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})^{2+}$. In analogy with $\text{Co}(\text{III})$ -tren systems studied previously, a structure with the amino acid nitrogen *trans* to the primary nitrogen of the tren ligand was assigned to the orange complex, although no structural data is available to support this assignment.

Preliminary studies suggest that isomeric complexes may also be formed with alanine ethyl ester.

Miller and Madan²³ found that the initial 10% of the first-order kinetics plot for the aquation of $\text{Co}(\text{tren})\text{ClH}_2\text{O}^{2+}$ was noticeably curved and that spectral scans showed a slight shift in isosbestic points during the first part of the reaction. The kinetic data could be separated, however into two first-order reactions. It was suggested that two isomers of $\text{Co}(\text{tren})\text{ClH}_2\text{O}^{2+}$ were present and could be reacting in parallel. Thin layer chromatography was used unsuccessfully in an attempt to separate any isomers present^{23a}.

Madan⁵⁰ prepared [Co(tren,ClBr)Br] by the following process¹⁴ and found

that the first-order kinetic plot for its aquation also had initial curvature, but could be resolved into two first-order reactions. Bromide ion was released only during the initial part of the reaction, and it was assumed, but could not be confirmed, that chloride was released throughout the reaction. The two first-order rate constants obtained for the aquation of [Co(tren)ClBr]⁺ ($k_\alpha = 3.21 \times 10^{-2} \text{sec}^{-1}$, $k_\beta = 3.38 \times 10^{-2} \text{sec}^{-1}$) agreed reasonably well with the k_1 values for the aquation of Co(tren)Br₂⁺ and Co(tren)Cl₂⁺ ($k_{1\text{Br}} = 2.8 \times 10^{-2} \text{sec}^{-1}$, $k_{1\text{Cl}} = 2.96 \times 10^{-2} \text{sec}^{-1}$). It was suggested that two isomers of the chlorobromo compound are present, and that the two first-order reactions are the loss of bromide and chloride from the position *cis* to the tertiary nitrogen on each isomer. However, elemental analysis of the compound [Co(tren)ClBr]Br would not establish whether any [Co(tren)Br₂]Cl was also present, which reacting along with the chlorobromo complex, could also explain the kinetics observed.

It seems, therefore, that isomers of Co(III) tren complexes do exist with certain amino acid esters as ligands, but the question of their existence in complexes containing simple monodentate ligands needs further investigation.

References

- 1.(a) F. G. MANN and W. J. POPE, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, (London) 1925, 109A, 444 ;
- (b) F. G. MANN and W. J. POPE, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 482 ; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 489.
2. S. G. ZIPP, A. P. ZIPP and S. K. MADAN, *Coord. Chem. Rep.*, 1974, 14, 29.
3. E. RISTENPART, *Ber.*, 1896, 20, 2526.
4. P. PAOLETTI, M. CIAMPOLINI and L. SACCONI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 3589.
5. E. KIMURA, S. YOUNG and J.P. COLLMAN, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1970, 9, 1183.
6. J. H. FORSBERG, T. M. KUBIK, T. MOELLER and K. GUCIVA, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1971, 10, 2656.
7. H. B. JONASSEN and V. V. RAMANIYAM, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1959, 63, 411.
8. L. V. INTERRANTE and J. L. SHAFER, unpublished results.
9. R. H. MIZZONI, M. A. HNNNESSEY and C. R. SCHOLZ, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 72, 2414.
10. W. J. KASOWSKI and J. C. BAILAR, JR., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, 91, 3212.

11. L. V. INTERRANTE, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1968, 7, 943.
12. P. C. JAIN, E.C. LINGAFELTER and P. PAOLETTI, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, 90, 579.
13. M. CLAMPOLINI and N. NARDI, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, 5, 1150.
14. L.V. INTERRANTE, *Inorg. Nuclear Chem. Letters*, 1968, 4, 411.
15. G. A. BARCLAY and A. K. BERNARD, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958 2540.
16. A. DEI and R. MORASSI, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1971, 2024.
17. M. CIAMPOLINI, N. NARDI and G. P. SPERONI, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1966, 1, 222.
18. L. SACCONI and R. MORASSI, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1969, 2904.
19. M. CIAMPOLINI, *Chem. Comm.*, 1966, 47.
20. I. BERTINI, M. CIAMPOLINI, P. DAPPORTO and D. GATTESCHI, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1972, 11, 2254.
21. K. N. RAYMOND and F. BASOLO, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, 5, 1632.
22. W. V. MILLER and S. K. MADAN, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1971, 10, 1250.
23. C. F. LU, Ph D. Thesis, U. of Illinois, 1957.
24. S. K. MADAN and J. PEONE, Jr, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1967, 6, 463.
25. K. KUO and S. K. MADAN, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1971, 10, 229.
26. K. KUO, W. V. MILLER and S. K. MADAN, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1973, 35, 957.
27. W. V. MILLER and S. K. MADAN, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1970, 9, 2362.
28. K. KUO and S. K. MADAN, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1969, 8, 1580.
29. H. A. SCHEIDEGGER, Doctoral Thesis, E.T.H., Zurich (1966).
30. J. P. COLLMAN and E. KIMURA, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, 89, 6096.
31. G. JLERUP, G. GOSEPHSEN, K. MICHELSEN, E. PEDERSEN and C. SCHAFER, *Acta. Chem. Scand.*, 1970, 24, 247.
32. E. PEDERSEN, *Acta. Chem. Scand.*, 1970, 24, 3362.
- 33.(a) S. G. ZIPP and S. K. MADAN, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1976, 15, 587.
- (b) S.G. ZIPP and S.K. MADAN, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1975, 37, 181 ;
- (c) J. R. GAYLOR and C. V. SENOFF, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1972, 11, 2551 ;
- (d) S. G. ZIPP and S. K. MADAN, *Inorg. Chim. Acta.*, 1975, 14, 83 ;
- (e) J. HUGHES and G. R. WILLEY, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 1974, 4, 33 ;
- (f) M. N. HUGHES and W. R. MCWHINNEE, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1967, 592.
34. S. E. RASMUSSEN, *Acta. Chem. Scand.*, 1959, 13, 2009.
35. E. C. COX and K. C. WEBSTER, *Z. Krist. A.*, 1935, 92, 478.
36. S. A. JOHNSON and F. BASOLO, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1962, 1, 925.
37. M. E. BALDWIN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 4369.
38. C. K. JØRGENSEN, *Acta. Chem. Scand.*, 1956, 10, 887.

39. S. K. MADAN and J. PEONE, JR., *Inorg. Chem.*, 1968, 7, 824.
40. BOGDANSKY, Ph.D. Thesis, SUNY-Buffalo (1972).
41. P. PAOLETTI and M. CIAMPOLINI, *Rec. Sci.*, [IIA], 1963, 33, 399.
42. M. CIAMPOLINI and N. NARDI, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, 5, 1150.
43. I. BERTINI, M. CIAMPOLINI, P. DAPPORTO and D. GATTESCHI, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1972, 11, 2254.
44. L. SACCONI, M. DiVAIRA and A. BIANCHI, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1970, 92, 4465.
45. M. F. JOHNSON, Ph. D., Thesis, St. Louis Univ., (1972).
46. D. HALL and M. D. WOULEF, *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 346.
47. S. E. RASMUSSEN and R. GRØNBAEK, *Acta. Chem. Scand.*, 1963, 17, 832.
48. P. C. JAIN and E. C. LINGAFELTER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, 89, 724.
49. M. D. VAIRA and P. L. ORIOLI, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1967, 6, 955.
50. S. YUAN, W. V. MILLER and S. K. MADAN, *Inorg. Chim. Acta.*, 1973, 7, 134.